

TABLE I. SENSITIVE TERMS IN THE DICTIONARY (TOP 200 RANKING BY INFORMATION GAIN RATIO)

soa	scalability	throughput
alternatives	penalty	scaling
versus	buffer	enterprise
modular	balancing	security
messaging	apps	timeout
notification	xmpp	heartbeat
distributed	performance	brokers
real-time	pattern	pros
retry	rollback	virtual
refactor	manipulation	runtime
MVC	client	cons
correctness	transferability	practicality
compliance	serviceability	optimize
useableness	movability	icons
default	cache	redundancy
Ping/Echo	monitor	balancing
voting	condition	shadow
restart	non-stop	self-test
reconfiguration	upgrade	transactions
collaborative	orchestrate	tailor
coupling	cohesion	encapsulate
deplorability	frustration	user
record	download	component
mechanism	occur	portability
minimal	graph	capability
clue	reuse	relational
j2ee	library	faster
redis	lightweight	choosing
wrapper	latency	FIFO
dynamic	static	advance
integrity	authentication	firewall
attacks	network	communicate
plus	outbound	isonlin
sparrpow	timewait	authentic
scheduler	vulnerability	running
log	adaptability	overflow
fixed-priority	scaling	vulnerability
checkpoint	security	trustworthy
layered	cutoff	policy
execution	optimize	interoperability
asynchrony	performance	transferability
memento	governing	optimization
observer	colon	usability
proxy	modular	operability
strategy	dependency	reliability
maptask	interdependent	failure
authority	understandability	administration
chain	functionality	HMAC
permiss	buffer	RBAC
poll	request	asynch
thread	authentication	loadbalancing
priority	standardized	rollback
session	authenticate	periodic
configuration	refresh	modify
audit	wizard	interrupt

coupling	deplorability	simplify
denial	sandbox	choosing
scheduler	scaling	progress
fixed-priority	security	slow
authent	pause	disposition
pool	optimize	isonlin
asynchrony	performance	brokers
regulation	reuse	pros
observer	maintainability	share
active-red	component-replacement	processor
scheduler-session	action	audit-trail